

PARACHOR OF FUSED RING STRUCTURE

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Parachors of *bicyclo*-(2 : 2 : 2)-octane-dione dicarboxylate and *bicyclo*-(3 : 2 : 2)-nonane-dione dicarboxylate have been determined. The compounds possess bicyclic ring structure containing 4 and 5 common carbon atoms, respectively. Both the compounds show a negative anomaly of about 4 to 6 units indicating thereby that the rings are in a strainless condition, probably possessing boat-shaped structures. Actual carbon models of these compounds support this assumption.

Evaluation of parachor has been widely used in characterising organic compounds. Work has also been done about the parachor of fused ring structure containing two or three carbon atoms common to more than one of the rings (Deshapande *et al.*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **19**, 157 ; Ray, *ibid.*, 1935, **12**, 764 ; Guha, *ibid.*, 1944, **21**, 339). But little or no information is available about the parachor of fused ring structure containing four or five common carbon atoms. This class of compounds is not easily available and is rather difficult to prepare. A determination of the parachor of these compounds is therefore interesting as it will throw some light on the stereochemical orientation and spatial

configuration of these molecules. In this paper the parachors of the following two compounds have been determined.

Bicyclo-(2:2:2)-octane-dione
dicarboxylate (I)

Bicyclo-(3:2:2)-nonane-dione
dicarboxylate (II)

The compounds were obtained according to the method of Guha (*Ber.*, 1939, 72, 1359). The compound (I) contains two fused six-membered rings with four common carbon atoms and the compound (II) is constituted of two fused seven-membered rings with five carbon atoms common to both the rings. As the substances are solid, surface tension was determined by maximum bubble-pressure method in nitrobenzene solution. To ensure the accuracy of the results, the instrumental constant was checked with pure anhydrous benzene before each measurement. Density was determined with a small pycnometer and parachor was calculated according to the equation of Hammick and Andrew (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 755).

Thus

$$P_m = P_s (1-x) + P_x x \quad \dots \quad \text{(I)}$$

$$P_m = \frac{M_m}{D-d} \gamma^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots \quad \text{(II)}$$

$$M_m = M_s (1-x) + M_x x \quad \dots \quad \text{(III)}$$

where P_m = parachor of solution, P_x = parachor of the solute, P_s = parachor of the solvent, x = molar fraction of the solute, $(1-x)$ = molar fraction of the solvent, M_m = mean molecular weight, D = density of the solution, γ = surface tension of the solution, M_s = molecular weight of the solvent, M_x = molecular weight of the solute. Mean parachor of nitrobenzene as determined with our instrument is 263.1. The value of 'g' at Bangalore was taken as 978. The parachor constant for a seven-membered ring was taken as 4.2 (Godchot, *Compt. rend.*, 1931, 192, 1560). A five-figured log-table was used in these calculations, because a small change in the value in P_m affects the result considerably. The density of the solutions of these compounds shows some unusual peculiarities which has been discussed at the end.

TABLE I

Parachor of bicyclo-(2 : 2 : 2)-octane-dione dicarboxylate in nitrobenzene solution.

$$P_{\text{calc.}} = 593.6.$$

Temp.	Density.	γ .	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .
			$x = 0.0158$		
30°	1.1941	42.35	125.5	268.10	589.1
40	1.1842	40.96	„	268.11	590.2
50	1.1743	39.60	„	268.09	588.5
			$x = 0.03718$		
30°	1.1941	42.12	129.0	275.22	588.92
40	1.1844	40.75	„	275.18	588.00
50	1.1746	39.49	„	275.32	591.70
			$x = 0.05121$		
30°	1.1943	42.024	131.27	279.85	590.1
40	1.1845	40.654	„	279.82	589.6
50	1.1747	39.242	„	279.69	587.1

Density-molar ratio relation

x .	D e n s i t y a t		
	30°	40°.	50°.
0.01528	1.1941	1.1842	1.1743
0.03718	1.1941	1.1844	1.1746
0.05121	1.1943	1.1847	1.1747

TABLE II

Parachor of bicyclo-(3 : 2 : 2)-nonane-dione dicarboxylate.

$$P_{\text{calc.}} = 628.80$$

Temp.	Density.	γ .	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .
			$x = 0.01621$		
30°	1.1944	42.36	125.91	268.94	622.8
40	1.1843	40.93	„	268.91	621.4
50	1.1747	39.60	„	268.88	620.1
			$x = 0.04012$		
30°	1.1944	42.21	130.06	277.55	623.1
40	1.1845	40.83	„	277.55	623.1
50	1.1748	39.54	„	277.60	624.4

Density-molar ratio relation

x .	D e n s i t y a t		
	30°.	40°	50°.
0.01621	1.1944	1.1843	1.1747
0.04012	1.1944	1.1845	1.1748

It is seen from the above results, that in the experimentally determined values of their parachor, both the compounds show a negative anomaly of about 4 to 6 units. This is an indication of the fact that these compounds exist in a strainless condition (Sugden, "Parachor and Valency", 1930, p. 44). In conformity with the work of Mohr (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1918, **98**, 315; 1922, **103**, 396) and others about strainless structure

of *cyclohexane* derivatives, the following strainless boat-shaped structures are therefore suggested for these compounds.

This suggestion is borne out by the fact that the actual carbon models of these compounds show similar orientation of the ring structure. One unusual peculiarity has been observed about the densities of these compounds. Though the amount of substance dissolved might vary considerably (1 : 5), the density at any particular temperature remained nearly identical. Thus the density remains almost unaffected by the amount of substance dissolved. This shows that by dissolving the substance in nitrobenzene, the volume adjustment takes place in such a way that the mass per unit volume at a particular temperature remains nearly constant.

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